

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY ON MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING AND COMPETENCIES OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS IN COOKERY

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ABSTRACT

The digitalized mode of teaching plays a vital role in today's education and provide opportunity in the development of 21st century skills. The study focused on the utilization of digital technology such as digitalized module, digitalized platform and materials in the face of modular distance learning. It aimed to assess the perception of the students on digital technology and its relationships with their cookery learning competencies as prescribed by Technical Vocational Development and Authority (TESDA). The level of competency in Cookery as perceived by the students, have revealed a positive correlation with the utilization of digital technology on modular distance learning. This provides a positive impact on the learning process of the students in which they are capable of demonstrating their knowledge and skill through portfolio presentation. The salient findings yielded, that the students who were involved in utilizing the digitalized module, platform and materials, has shown a significantly greater improvement in learning Cookery. Facebook and messenger as the used platforms for delivering the instructions have served as the pathway for good communication and relationship between the teacher and the students. This provides learning opportunity for every student to become optimistic and resilient to continue their education even in the hardest time. This result allows the students to learn on their own pace, time and place. Based on the findings of the study, the following are hereby recommended: The teacher-researcher may engage in professional development activities; the school may conduct training-workshop among teachers to develop related electronic teaching materials; the school may support the researcher in encouraging the parents and students to engage and get in touch with the teacher on how to use the electronic material provided by the teacher. The school may also adopt the social media such as Facebook and Messenger as an alternative contextualized learning platform to supplement and integrate teaching instrument that will engage learners on modular distance learning.

Keywords: digital technology, cookery, learning competency, modular distance learning